

TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSTICS OF LYMPHANGIOMAS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: *Lymphangiomas are tumor-like formations, the genesis of which is associated with malformations of embryonic lymphatic sacs during their formation and differentiation. Lymphangiomas arise as a result of malformations of the lymphatic system in the embryo, starting from the 6th week of pregnancy. Due to the genetic relationship of lymphangiomas to blood vessels, in particular, to the venous system, their radical removal presents certain difficulties, where they are located close to the main vessels of the neck, axillary region, mediastinum and other localizations.*

Keywords: *lymphangioma, children, sclerotherapy, surgical treatment.*

Macroscopically, they consist of lymphatic cavities of different sizes containing lymph. The inner surface of the cavities is lined mainly with vascular endothelium, in some places where it is absent, the lining is represented by mesenchymal tissue.

Lymphangiomas can be external (cervical, cervical axillary-thoracic) and internal (mediastinal, internal organs, retroperitoneal, pelvic). Most often, lymphangiomas are located in the zones of embryonic development of the lymphatic system: neck, axillary region, retrosternal space. The most common lymphangiomas are cervical localization, which make up from 74 to 82% (25-2000). Lymphangiomas are also found in other anatomical areas of the body. In addition to the cervical, they can be cervicothoracic (24-2000), and are also found in the mediastinum in the abdominal organs (22-2001), retroperitoneal space (17-2001), pelvis. Cervicothoracic lymphangiomas occur in 6% of patients (24-2000), mediastinal localization - in 10-16% of patients, in the abdominal organs - in 1-2% (22-2001), retroperitoneal location - in 1-2% (17-2001), pelvic localization - in 1-2% of patients.

In accordance with the objectives of the dissertation research (increasing the radicality of lymphangioma removal, stage-by-stage excision, compliance with the principles of cosmetic surgery), a critical analysis of domestic and foreign publications, mainly of the last 15 years, in one way or another touching upon these aspects of surgical treatment of lymphangiomas in children was carried out. First of all, we consider it appropriate to cover the current state of the problem of the radicality of removal of lymphangiomatous tumors in children. Literature sources indicate that relapses of lymphangiomas occur in 6 - 10.68% of cases. In addition, it should be noted that relapses occur mainly when it is necessary to leave areas of tumor tissue on large vessels, nerves, trachea, pericardium, i.e. in anatomically complex areas. Mechanical removal of lymphangiomatous tissue from these vital anatomical formations is almost impossible without damaging them with the development of serious complications, mainly bleeding, up to and including death. A number of authors express an erroneous, in our opinion,

opinion that when removing lymphangiomas, one should not strive for their radical excision. According to these authors, it is enough to remove the main part of the tumor tissue, leaving some of it on large vascular trunks and vital organs, wiping with alcohol and stitching with nylon, and one can count on a stable long-term result. In this regard, the problem of the radicality of surgical intervention in the excision of lymphangiomas still remains one of the most pressing. Due to the genetic relationship of lymphangiomas to blood vessels, in particular, to the venous system, their radical removal presents certain difficulties, where they are located close to the main vessels of the neck, axillary region, mediastinum and other localizations. In this regard, lymphangiomatous tissue, which is difficult to remove and therefore remains on large vascular trunks, serves as a source of tumor relapses, which occur from 6.4% to 7.6%. In this connection, attempts are being made to chemically influence such areas of tumor tissue. In the treatment of small superficial lymphangiomas, some authors use alcohol, quinine urethane, OK-432 (15-2000; 23-2000), Bleomycin, and Etiblok skin embolization of lymphangiomatous cysts as sclerosing therapy. Sclerosing therapy (76° alcohol and 0.25% novocaine solution in a 1:3 ratio) was part of a combination treatment that was administered to 8 patients with extensive tumors that could not be completely removed surgically.

In recent years, a number of publications have appeared, primarily among pediatric otolaryngologists, on the conservative use of various sclerosing agents (14,15-2000) for the treatment of neck lymphangiomas extending to the submandibular region and face. We analyzed the studies of authors with the largest number and deepest study of clinical observations.

In the studies of C. Brewis et al. (2000), the drug OK-432 (Picibanil) was used to treat 11 children with head and neck lymphangiomas over the period from 1996 to 1998. OK-432 is a lyophilized mixture of a low-virulence strain of streptococcus (*Streptococcus pyogenes*) and benzylpenicillin. Mechanism of action: OK-432 causes aseptic inflammation of the intima of the tumor walls, which leads to their fusion and suppression of lymph production. According to other authors, OK-432 leads to an increase in the number of leukocytes in the tumor due to neutrophils and macrophages that produce biologically active substances - cytokines that increase the permeability of the endothelium of the lymphangiomatous walls and enhance the outflow of lymph from the tumor cavities. We like the first point of view, since there is an indisputable clinical fact of lymphangioma regression after its inflammation associated not with the introduction of Picibanil, but with the intratumor development of a banal endogenous infection. Before the introduction of the drug, children underwent computed tomography or magnetic resonance scanning. A single dose of the drug - 0.2 mg in 20 ml of saline (no more) was injected into the lymphangioma after lymph aspiration under anesthesia. In 2 patients, complete tumor regression was achieved, in 2 - significant regression, in 5 - insignificant regression, in 2 - no effect. Thus, complete and significant regression was achieved in 4 patients (36.4%). In 6 patients, surgery had been performed previously, i.e., the tumor recurred. In 10 people, complications were obtained in the form of fever (6 children), local inflammation (3 patients) and abscess (1 child).

The researchers present the combined statistics of 7 authors on the treatment of lymphangiomas with this drug in 105 patients: - 64 patients, - 2, - 12, - 5, - 11-6-5 patients; 47 children achieved complete regression, 21 - significant regression, 16 - minor regression, 21 - no effect. Thus, 68 patients (65%) achieved complete and significant regression. The authors believe that complete removal of the tumor by surgery is usually impossible, hence the high percentage of relapses noted by surgeons. As follows from the conclusion of the authors of the article, on their own material, numbering 11 patients, 63.6% of patients received unsatisfactory results, which indicates the weak effectiveness of the drug OK-432.

The second group of authors (M.Emran, J.Dubois, L.Laberge, A.Al-Jazaeri, A.Butter, S.Yazbeck, 2006) used the method of introducing ethiblok (an alcohol solution of zein) as a sclerosing agent in 63 patients with lymphangiomas of various external localizations. Under general anesthesia, the lymph was aspirated by puncturing the lymphangiomatous cysts, then this drug was introduced in an amount of 10% of the tumor cyst volume. After such a sclerotherapy session, all patients had a general reaction in the form of fever and a local inflammatory reaction, which required anti-inflammatory therapy. In 84% of patients, excellent and good results were obtained with significant tumor regression, in 16% - the results were assessed as poor. The authors believe that such treatment can be carried out in patients with relapses after surgery, and also to select patients with poor results of ethiblok treatment for surgical treatment.

The third group of authors used bleomycin (antibiotic) fat emulsion as a sclerosing agent in 33 patients with cervical-submandibular, axillary, thoracic and mediastinal lymphangiomas. The technique of intratumoral administration of bleomycin emulsion was used. Satisfactory results were obtained in 27 patients, confirmed clinically and morphologically. The authors conclude that tumor infiltration with bleomycin is indicated in patients 1) with relapse after surgical treatment; 2) with the purpose of selecting patients for further surgical treatment; 3) with cystic forms of lymphangiomas; 4) with cervical, facial and axillary lymphangiomas, which usually have a better cosmetic result compared to surgical treatment.

In the works of M.Emran et al. (2006) and other authors who used chemical action of various preparations on lymphangiomatous tissue in lymphangiomas of the neck and face, noted that during surgical removal of tumors of these localizations, up to 17% of neurological complications were encountered, mainly associated with trauma to the n.GaslaNB at the site of its exit in front of the auricle onto the face. In this regard, these authors consider this localization of lymphangiomas to be one of the indications for the use of sclerosing agents, excluding postoperative paralysis of the facial nerve and related corrective plastic surgeries.

Summarizing the current state of chemical and biological action on lymphangiomas, the most effective were an alcohol solution of zein and a fat emulsion of bleomycin, the use of which in patients with complex anatomical localization of lymphangiomas gave positive results in more than 80% of patients. Clinical studies have shown that it is

advisable to use biological and chemical agents to affect lymphangiomatous tissue in the following situations: 1) in case of relapses of surgical removal of lymphangiomas; 2) in case of certain morphological types of lymphangiomas; 3) in order to select patients for further surgical treatment; 4) for combined treatment of lymphangiomas of complex anatomical localizations, when these drugs are used simultaneously with surgical techniques to suppress tumor growth in places that present difficulties for surgeons (submandibular region) and the risk of damage to the nerve trunks of the facial muscles (n. facialis).

Recently, the issue of the stages of lymphangioma removal has been increasingly raised (12-2009), however, a consensus on this issue has not been reached among the majority of pediatric surgeons. One group of authors considers it appropriate to remove some lymphangiomas (in particular, those of cervical mediastinal localization) in several stages with an interval of 16 days, using the anterolateral intercostal approach. Many authors (12-2007) consider such an approach to be insufficiently justified, since it seems technically difficult to remove lymphangiomatous tissue from large vascular trunks of the mediastinum (superior vena cava, brachiocephalic trunks, subclavian vessels) and pericardium and recommend using a partial median sternotomy in the form of an inverted letter T. The above-mentioned pediatric surgeons themselves write about the disadvantages of the intercostal approach. Endoscopic removal of mediastinal lymphangiomas is out of the question. One-stage removal of a giant cavernous lymphangioma in a child, located on the left lateral surface of the chest and abdomen, starting from the axillary region to the inguinal fold. The staging of surgical treatment of large tumors is also followed for the staging of removal of lymphangiomas of the cervico-facial localization. Lymphangiomas of the mediastinum in children are observed in 16% of mediastinal tumors. According to other authors (Gross; Ellis et Du Shane), they are somewhat less common - up to 7-10%. Mediastinal lymphangiomas and lymphhemangiomas are located in the upper third of the anterior mediastinum in the area of large venous trunks. The clinical picture of the tumor depends primarily on its location and size. Naturally, when the lymphangioma is located in the upper third of the retrosternal space, symptoms of compression of the trachea and large venous trunks (truncus venosus brachiocephalicus, v. cava sup.) by the tumor appear quite early: difficulty breathing, dyspnea, cough, attacks of cyanosis and swelling of the face, swelling of the jugular veins, the appearance of a collateral venous network of the upper half of the body, Stokes syndrome. Clinical observations with fatal outcomes due to rapid enlargement of the lymphangioma associated with its inflammation and pressure on the vascular formations of the mediastinum have been described (Balbaa et Chesterman; Bergstrom).

Due to the fairly frequent cervical-mediastinal localization of lymphangiomas, one of the clinical symptoms is its bulging in the neck above the jugular notch of the sternum or above the clavicle. In this case, its size changes synchronously with the act of breathing of the child.

The decisive method of research is computed tomography, which allows to determine the size of the largest tumor mass and its prevalence, as well as the relationship with the vascular formations of the mediastinum. Surgical intervention of mediastinal lymphangiomas is associated with traumatization of large venous trunks and intraoperative bleeding. Even such a master of pediatric surgery as E.A. Stepanov, and then in 2 observations describes the injury of the superior and inferior vena cava with severe bleeding during surgery, which in one case ended in death.

During partial removal of cystic lymphangioma, the remaining tumor fragments were treated with iodine and stitched with silk in order to disrupt blood circulation in them. Remote results up to 7 years are good. No less difficult task is diagnostics and treatment of lymphangiomas of the abdominal organs, mediastinum and retroperitoneal space. Treatment of extensive lymphangiomas of various localizations and at present presents certain difficulties. Until now, some issues of surgical treatment of lymphangiomas in children of various localizations remain debatable and require further clarification and resolution, which confirms the relevance of the problem. Finally, we consider it necessary to dwell on the issues of cosmetics associated with the removal of lymphangiomas, especially external location. They acquire special importance when removing extensive tumors occupying several anatomical areas. Issues of a cosmetology plan appeared only in publications of recent years and are represented by single studies of this plan. At the same time, the cosmetic side of surgical interventions has begun to occupy not the last place among the features of operations to remove lymphangiomas at present. The cosmetology side of such operations in the case of lymphangioma of the neck with vessels, it is preferable to use a longitudinal approach. If it is localized outside the connection with the vessels, the transverse approach should be used as it is more cosmetic.

References

1. Гариб Ф.Ю. и др. Иммунозависимые болезни. Ташкент, 1996.
2. Мамадалиев А.М. и др. Клинико-неврологические особенности интрацеребральных опухолей больших полушарий головного мозга // Вестник неврологии, психиатрии и нейрохирургии, 2015. № 9. С. 73-78.
3. Норкулов Н.У., Шодиев А.Ш., Норкулов С.Н. Особенности диагностики и лечения опухолей мозжечка // XX Давиденковские чтения, 2018. С. 293-294.
4. Ортиков А.А. и др. Совершенствование хирургического лечения гемангиом полости носа и глотки // Достижения науки и образования, 2020. № 1 (55). 100
5. Шодиев А.Ш., Норкулов Н.У., Норкулов С.Н. Клинические особенности течения опухолей мозжечка у детей // XX Давиденковские чтения, 2018. С. 443-443.
6. Шамсиев А.М. и др. Опухолевидные образования у детей первых месяцев жизни // Тюменский медицинский журнал, 2011. № 2.

7. Шамсиев А.М., Атакулов Ж.А., Лёнюшкин А.М. Хирургические болезни детского возраста // Ташкент: Из-во «Ибн-Сино, 2001.
8. Шамсиев А.М., Хамраев А.Ж. Малая хирургия детского возраста. Ташкент: Изд-во O'qituvchi, 2006.
9. Шаханова Ш.Ш., Пардаев Д.Б.У., Рахимов Ж.Х. Дифференциальная диагностика клиничко-лучевых признаков гигантоклеточной опухоли и остеосаркомы // Достижения науки и образования, 2020. № 1 (55).
10. Slepov V.P. et al. Use of ethonium in the combined treatment of suppurative and inflammatory diseases in children // Klinicheskaja khirurgija, 1981. № 6. С. 78.
11. Shamsiyev A.M., Khusinova S.A. The Influence of Environmental Factors on Human Health in Uzbekistan // The Socio-Economic Causes and Consequences of Desertification in Central Asia. Springer, Dordrecht, 2008. С. 249-252
12. Sh, Abdurakhmanov D. "Clinical and instrumental characteristics of postoperative ventral hernias in choosing the optimal method of plastic surgery." Achievements of science and education 1 (2020): 55.
13. Mamadiyarovich I. A. Diagnosis and Treatment of Foreign Body in The Respiratory Tract in Children //Journal of Science in Medicine and Life. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1-5.
14. Isakov A. Modern technologies of treatment of bronchiectasis in children //Центральноазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 13-19.
15. OGLi N. A. M. et al. Results of surgical treatment of intaoperative injuries of magisterial bile ducts //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 13 (97). – С. 98-107.
16. Mardonov, B. A., Isakov, A. M., Bahriev, B. L., & Kurbaniyazova, A. Z. POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIA: CURRENT STATUS OF THE PROBLEM.
17. Шамсиев, Ж. А., Махмудов, З. М., Боберов, К. Р., Исаков, А. М., & Шамсиев, Б. М. (2020). НЕОТЛОЖНЫЕ МЕРОПРИЯТИЯПРИ АБДОМИНАЛЬНОЙ ТРАВМЕ У ДЕТЕЙ. Российский вестник детской хирургии, анестезиологии и реаниматологии, 10(S), 194-194.
18. Norjigitovich, N. Z., Mamadiyarovich, I. A., Karamatovich, S. F., Arzikulovich, Y. P., & Umidovich, I. S. (2020). Modified method of plasmopheresis in the treatment patients with purulent cholangitis. Вопросы науки и образования, (13 (97)), 108-114.
19. Шамсиев, Ж. А., Саидов, М. С., Исаков, А. М., Данияров, Э. С., & Махмудов, З. М. ДИАГНОСТИКА, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ И РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ДЕТЕЙ С АНОРЕКТАЛЬНЫМИ МАЛЬФОРМАЦИЯМИ.

20. Шамсиев, А. М., Шамсиев, Ж. А., Махмудов, З. М., & Исаков, А. М. (2021). УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ РАННЕЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ОСТРОГО ГЕМАТОГЕННОГО ОСТЕОМИЕЛИТА КОСТЕЙ ТАЗОБЕДРЕННОГО СУСТАВА У ДЕТЕЙ. *Детская хирургия*, 25(S1), 81-81.
21. Amirovich, M. B., Mamadiyarovich, I. A., Karamatovich, S. F., & Arzikulovich, Y. P. (2020). Optimization of treatment of patients with ventral hernia. *Academy*, (3 (54)), 109-116.
22. Бабаяров, К. Р., Унабоев, Ж. О., Дусяров, Ж. Т., & Исаков, А. М. (2023). Достижения И Проблемы Педиатрической Анестезиологии И Интенсивной Терапии. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(6), 287-291.
23. Шамсиев, А. М., Шамсиев, Ж. А., Давранов, Б. Л., Исаков, А. М., Давлатов, С. С., Махмудов, Б. Б., & Рахимов, А. К. (2020). Лечение лимфангиом у детей. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (7 (91)), 90-100.
24. Isakova, A. I., and Isakov AM. "Trudoustrojstvo vypusknikov vuza kak kriterij kachestva podgotovki specialistov [Employment of University graduates as a criterion for the quality of training]. *Sovremennye tendencii razvitiya nepreryvnogo obrazovaniya: vyzovy cifrovoj ekonomiki [Current trends in the development of continuing education: challenges of the digital economy. Proc of the international scientific and methodological conference].*" Tomsk. TUSUR (2020): 153-154.
25. Исакова А. И., Исаков А. М. Трудоустройство выпускников вуза как критерий качества подготовки специалистов //Современные тенденции развития непрерывного образования: вызовы цифровой экономики. – 2020. – С. 153-154.
26. Исаков А. М., Небрятенко Д. Ю. Об организации научно-исследовательского сектора при работе по методологии SUPERPAVE //Вестник Кыргызско-Российского Славянского университета. – 2020. – Т. 20. – №. 12. – С. 111-117.

